

Docere, Delectare, Mouere: the practical application of ancient Rhetoric in Durham Cathedral Priory

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Abstract:

This paper aims to discuss the influence of ancient Epistolarity and Rhetoric in the political, societal, educational, and diplomatic roles of medieval letter-writing practices. It will present new evidence of the practical utilisation of ancient letter collections and ancient rhetorical manuals in the daily educational and professional life of the English people living in Northumbria, specifically, near Durham Cathedral Priory. To do so, this paper will discuss the books found at Durham's chancery, called *Le Spendement*, in 1421. Durham was a medium-sized community in the Northeast of England, and it was a cultural and diplomatic centre in which people from several places (e.g. Denmark, Norway, Scotland, Ireland, Wales, Frankia, and minor German kingdoms) encountered the English to make political and economic agreements. Nevertheless the lack of universities or great educational centres, Durham Cathedral Priory invested heavily in the intellectual and professional formation of the local people, including laypeople and Benedictine monks. Therefore, as this paper will show, teaching letter-writing practices based on ancient theories, examples and manuals, guaranteed Durham to grow in all aspects, but mainly in the literacy levels and political and societal institutions based on the ability of reading and writing all sorts of rhetorical and philosophical letters.

1. Introduction

In this article, I intend to demonstrate how beneficial it is to revisit the medieval reception and reapplication of ancient Rhetoric from a multidisciplinary approach. Far from a theoretical discussion on the aspects of imitation, emulation, and adaption of certain ancient rhetorical features by medieval people, I will argue that medieval Rhetoric was a continuation of late ancient Christian Authors who heavily relied on Ciceronian Oratory. Examining ancient Roman and Greek practices and theories as constant humane

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issues that evolve and shift according to new realities can provide new understandings of Antiquity and how we comprehend our own history.

To limit this examination to something feasible, I will concentrate on a group of books catalogued in Durham's chancery, called *Le Spendement*, in 1421. Among the 16 books a monk named John Fyshburn listed to be found there, we will delve into a specific manuscript (C.IV.25) that contains the book IV of *Rhetorica Ad Herennium*, Geoffrey of Vinsaulf's *Documentum de Arte et Modo Versificandi*, a brief explanation on the parts of the letters, a treatise on preaching, and a *tractatus dictaminis* (TD from now onwards). The latter was written by a monk named William of Whallay, who penned this treatise to be used by young boys taught at the chancery. Then, I will propose a metaphor using Cicero's triad to offer three distinct approaches to understanding the echoes of Ciceronian theories in late medieval Durham.

To comprehend ancient Rhetoric in practice in the Middle Ages, we need to establish some axioms. First, for us, ancient Rhetoric practices are perceivable only through the written versions of speeches delivered weeks or even months before their publication due to the time needed to amend imprecisions, rewrite passages that had failed during the initial delivery, and increase what was successful. Nonetheless, ancient Rhetoric should be heard, and, in some cases, the delivery should be seen, not read in silence and alone. Second, most western European people had a unique source of truth, moral precepts, and understanding: the Catholic church in the name of the Christian God. Even though they might not fully believe in it, it was a societal and legal requirement to accept and to declare such a creed; therefore, the speaker, the dictator, or the scribe were just channelling God's words and interpreting them correctly, which should be followed unquestionably and permanently. Third, in the medieval world, writing was just established as the primary source of knowledge and daily bureaucratic activities, in which writing was preferably done in a second language, not the mother and vernacular language.

In that sense, we must look to letter-writing manuals to significantly understand the ancient Rhetoric in the Middle Ages. The practice of composing letters was used to compose all sorts of documents and speeches, and it was intertwined with Rhetoric, Grammar (mostly phonetics), and Poetry. Moreover, epistolography's heavy influence on composing prose texts is directly connected to the development of Catholicism in late

Antiquity, in which letter-writing was the most common and versatile genre of writing used for personal, professional, and political purposes.

2. Durham and Northeast England: education, growth, wealth.

Durham, a palatinate county with a massive Cathedral and a Benedictine Priory in Northeast England, was a region of strategic importance, cultural diversity, and economic prosperity². Durham's location near the Scottish border made it a critical defensive site for England, as evidenced by its castles and fortifications. It also maintained a politically neutral stance when England had to deal with the Highlanders and established diplomatic and commercial ties with continental people, especially Scandinavians. Due to that multicultural and mixed linguistic³ and societal reality, Durham was a flourishing part of the British Island, where Scandinavians, Scottish, Irish, Welsh, Normans, and Anglo-Saxons cohabitated in various degrees between peace and war. In that context, Durham Cathedral Priory engaged in various administrative and diplomatic activities, making it a versatile agent with extensive political experience and considerable legal expertise in several fields⁴.

From that power, the necessity of offices, courts, and chanceries arose fast⁵. Thus, Durham Cathedral Priory established a chancery, a court for small and medium cases related to local matters, and offices to produce administrative documents⁶. All those bureaucratic structures needed men who could read and write to work in those places. Due to the need for educated individuals in various roles within offices, courts, and chanceries, the proficient reading and writing of Latin were necessary for professional and spiritual growth in Durham and the broader northeast region of England⁷. The

² The most recent and solid studies on medieval Durham are Claxton2020; Brown 2015; Dobie 2015; Boyd 2013; Threlfall-Holmes 2005; Kirk 1991; Dobson 1973.

³ The manuscripts in Durham show that Latin, English, and French were frequently used, at least in written documents. There are also a few manuscripts in Greek and some texts in Germanic languages. Besides that, by the people who circulated in northeast England, we may expect that some people spoke Italian, Danish, Welsh, Irish, and Scottish Gaelic languages.

⁴ On this matter, see Haskett 1996, p. 247-253

⁵ According to Patt 1978, p. 134, "In actuality, however, its most important aspect was the teaching and practice of letter-writing. One can distinguish at least two main reasons for this utilitarian tendency. First, letter-writing was one of the most common forms of composition practiced in the Middle Ages. Second, the *ars dictaminis* offered one of the few opportunities for a career in administration, government, and politics. The seats of power, the ecclesiastical and secular chanceries, and courts, were accessible to those with training in law, theology, or *ars dictaminis*. Because the *ars dictaminis* was so indispensable, it was taught in cathedral and monastic schools, and later in the universities, all over Europe".

⁶ On the powers granted to Durham Cathedral Priory, see Claxton 2020 and Boyd 2013.

⁷ Orme (2006) and Orme (2015) are the better references for studying Middle Ages schools in Northeast England. However, Thomson & Morgan (2008) and Greatrex (1991) are also excellent references for

magnitude of the educational system there can be stressed by the significant financial investments made in the education of monks, novices, and even secular boys⁸. The focus was Latin Grammar and Song. We have no information about other disciplines that may be taught in northeast England. The training served first to prepare laypeople and clerics to aptly exert daily duties in any social, juridical, political, or ecclesiastical institution⁹; secondly, the primary studies led the most apt men to be funded in Oxford¹⁰.

In Durham's case, although not always completing degrees, the monks and laypeople who pursued higher studies at Oxford acquired valuable skills to pursue diverse careers in offices and courts. Their training encompassed the art of letter-writing, preaching, and ancient Rhetoric, including giving sermons, working at the chancery and courts, and supporting the Bishop and the Prior. Notably, the last seven priors of the monastery held doctorates in theology and had previously served as wardens of Durham College¹¹.

3. Durham's *Le Spendement*

The establishment of a medieval chancery, such as the one within Durham Cathedral Priory, was rooted in the evolving administrative and legal practices of the Middle Ages and the revaluations of the importance of writing¹². These institutions were fundamental to the administration of medieval Europe, and their origins can be traced back to the bureaucratic systems of the late Roman Empire. Understanding this historical context is crucial for comprehending the evolution of chanceries and their role in the governance structures of the early medieval period.

understanding education in the Middle Ages. For the teaching of secular boys, see Surtees Society 1842, p. 81. For Latin's social and professional uses and the pedagogical outline of Latin teaching, see Cornelius 2010.

⁸ For the amount Durham Cathedral Priory invested in education, see Claxton 2020 and Orme 2015. For instance, Orme 2015, p. 437, states that "In 1286, Durham began to acquire land at Oxford on which to build a house for student monks, and this house duly came into existence Durham College," which was a pioneer and lonely entrepreneur.

⁹ Cornelius 2010, p. 298, says that "The ostensible purpose of such instruction was to ensure that the letter proceeded in a manner appropriate to its circumstances and hence to maximize the sender's chances of receiving favourable hearing. However, the specifically codified form taken by this instruction lent the instruction a slightly different function: by providing a menu of ready-made and approved formulas, the *ars dictaminis* spared chancery clerks and notaries from the task of making independent judgments concerning matters of social decorum." For other studies, see also Clanchy 2013.

¹⁰ On the Northern English people funded to go universities, see Claxton 2020 and Greatrex 1991.

¹¹ On the education of several Priors and Bishops in Durham, see Boyd 2013, p. 21-25.

¹² On the development of literacy as a response to societal needs, see Patt 1978 and Clanchy 2013.

By the late medieval era, chanceries had become sophisticated centres of administrative excellence, staffed by skilled professionals well-versed in Latin and vernacular¹³. Their functions and influence were significantly shaped through interactions with various institutions. The royal court, for instance, relied heavily on the chancery for formalising decisions and proclamations. Churches collaborated closely with chanceries in managing ecclesiastical arrangements, legal decrees, and administrative decisions. These interactions fostered a complex web of influence and communication, reflecting the interconnected nature of medieval governance and societal structures.

In Durham's case, the establishment of the chancery within the library, nominated as *Le Spendement*¹⁴, accentuated the institution's commitment to education and the intellectual formation of the northern English community. Most persons who worked in Durham were born, raised, or studied near the Tyne and Wear region. Furthermore, selecting this secluded location ensured that valuable documents and books remained beyond the reach of unauthorised individuals and favoured focusing on producing documents and training people to compose those documents in a safe place to develop both administrative and educational work.

Within the confines of the *Spendement*, an assortment of materials, including excerpts and commentary on Canon and Civil Law, letter models, and writing manuals, were available to facilitate the composition and examination of legal and political documents. Moreover, these resources served the formal communication needs of Durham Cathedral's Prior. The meticulous catalogue by John Fyshburn in 1421 enumerates the following books¹⁵¹⁶:

A) CARTUARIUM PRIMUM, de Specialibus Munimentis infra Diocesim Dunelmensem. Secundo Folio "Edwardus";

B) CARTUARIUM SECUNDUM, de Generalibus Munimentis per Angliam. Secundo Folio "Carlixus";

C) CARTUARIUM TERCIMUM, de Munimentis Specialibus et Generalibus infra Diocesim Eboracensem et Lincolniensem. Secundo Folio "in capellis";¹⁷

¹³ On the construction of medieval chanceries and courts, see Constable 1992. On the requirement to work on chanceries and courses, see Cornelius 2010.

¹⁴ Gameson 2010, p. 19, calls the *Spendement* "the strong room off the northwest corner of the cloister". CLAXTON 2020, p. 25, says that "the *Spendement* as The most valuable books were kept in the "spendement", or treasury, a special storeroom for valuables off the west alley of the cloister".

¹⁵ The surviving manuscripts can be found digitalised at www.durhampriory.ac.uk.

¹⁶ SURTEES SOCIETY 1838, p. 123-4.

¹⁷ The cartularies were volumes meticulously organised to house copies or transcripts of significant charters, deeds, and legal documents, particularly those related to land ownership, privileges, and rights.

D) QUARTUM CARTUARIUM ANTIQUUM, de Munimentis Generalibus quod vocabatur LIBER TERRARII. Secundo Folio “nonice”;

E) REGISTRUM PRIMUM, de Dimissionibus terrarium per Capitulum factis, et confirmacionibus Dimissionum Episcoporum. Secundo Folio “anno Domini 1304”;

F) REGISTRUM SECUNDUM, de Literis sigillatis Sigillo communi et Prioris, cum aliis Recordis, a tempore Antonii Episcopi. Secundo Folio, “ydoneos”;

G) REGISTRUM TERCIMUM, in quaterno, de materiis antedictis, incompletum. Secundo Folio “pateat”.

H) Libellus THOMAE MELSONBY, qui vocatur LANDMAYBOKE. Secundo folio “Adam Cartar”;

I) Summa Dictaminis THOMAE DE CAPUWAY Cardinals. Secundo folio, “malum”;

K) Liber Continens PLACITA inter Willielmum Archiepiscopum Eboracensem et Capitulum Dunelmensem super formam visitandi, Sede Vacante. Secundo Folio, “tam simplices.”;

L) REGISTRUM papireum diversarum Literarum, in quodam volumine libri ligati. Secundo Folio, “cedentes”;¹⁸

M) Summa RICARDI BRITONIS de Legibus Anglicanis, continens octo libros, cum Tractatu de Natura Brevium et Statutis. Secundo folio, ‘tudinis non est’;

N) REGISTRUM papireum diversarum Literarum, cum tabula precedente. III. Folio “nobis et monachis”;¹⁹

Durham’s compilations served as a centralised repository, easing land management and taxation management, and preserving its crucial historical and legal records. They presented detailed descriptions and indexes, a precious historical and administrative resource. They were the first items on the list, A to D. Letter D of the list is currently missing; however, the three surviving manuscripts are in fair condition. Letters A, B and C are catalogued as Durham Cathedral Archive Cartulary 2, 1 and 3, respectively. There are also two other cartulary books in the Durham Cathedral Archive, but they do not display the first word of the second folio as described by Fyshburn. The manuscript listed as D has likely been dismembered and reinserted within other manuscripts, which makes it impossible to firmly ascertain if D was the current Cartulary 4. by type of addressee (Cartulary 1) or by subject (Cartulary 2 and 3).

¹⁸ Book L is now found at Durham Cathedral Archive. Other folios were inserted into it, but due to the comments of dozens of previous librarians on books and registers at the Archive, it is now possible to identify it as MS C.IV.25. It is a book with letter models, treatises on prosimetrum, letter-writing and Rhetoric. Book L draws attention because it is a rare case of a book produced in the same place it was used, as one can see from the autographed pedagogical material *Tractatus Dictaminis*, written by a monk named William of Whalley. That work does references to York rhetors, creates paraphrasis using deictic references, and is intended to be used by Durham boys.

¹⁹ There are three *Registri* dedicated to official documents encompassing communications with fellow church members and political dignitaries within England and abroad. There are also formal registers of legal and social transactions involving Durham Cathedral Priory. The list represents them by letters E, F and G. The *Registri* exhibits clear lettering devoid of embellishments, marginal notes, or rubrics. Only marginal indications of each excerpt’s content are discernible. These books serve as duplicates of official letters and documents penned in the name of Durham or directed to Durham, serving as references for consultation and modelling. We can find letter N, however dismembered with some new parts, including a treatise on *Dictamen* in extremely poor condition, yet to be confirmed the authorship and provenance. It suggests that, at some point, more books containing letter-writing treatises were brought to the chancery after 1421. Thus, we may assume that the chancery was running and growing in a number of books.

O) Cronica de Exordio et Progressu ECCLESIAE DUNELMENSIS, in quaterno. II folio “et quam maxime”.

P) Summa Dictaminis Monachi RICARDI DE POPHIS et Constitutiones Sinodales ECCLESIAE DUNELMENSIS ac Constitutiones Octoboni Legati, cum multis aliis. II folio “deus ut solitum”.²⁰

Q) Principium Tabulae Juris Canonici, continens duas literas tantum, videlicet A et B. Et quaedam Glosa super Constitutiones Clementinas, compliati per Magistrum THOMAM WALKYNGTON. II folio, “glosae de 9 di 5”²¹

R) REGISTRUM Diversarum Literarum, in quodam parvo volumine ligato. II. Folio “diffinico ire”

S) Summa AZONIS super Codicem, cum Institutionibus litera S.²²

Registers and cartularies served multiple purposes²³. They were historical records from decisions and legal and social agreements that guided Durham’s laws and moral principles in cases involving the Cathedral, its bishop, its prior, and its community. Secondly, they served as examples for writing similar documents²⁴. Nonetheless, what is interesting to us is the fact that these books taught jurisprudence to new scribes, *dictatores*, and students. The most recent letters and register in those books were likely

²⁰ The book, which has the work of Ricardus de Pophis, currently resides in the British Library, with only an old, microfilmed copy retained in Durham. Records indicate that this manuscript is the sole book from Fyshburn’s list departing from the Priory. The manuscript shows brown, red, and blue ink, decorated side margins, and prominent initial letters at the beginnings of paragraphs. It includes a compilation of various letter models and glossaries. This manuscript was probably composed abroad and later acquired to augment Durham Cathedral libraries. The absence of a similar manuscript in Durham covering prose and versification accentuates the willingness of Durham’s monks to acquire educational material for chancery use.

²¹ The manuscript holding the work of Thomas Melsonby stays conspicuously absent from digitalised collections and the Cathedral archive. There is no sign of its survival based on the reference “Adam Cartar” as the first words of the second folio. Nevertheless, finding portions of such texts dispersed within other manuscripts, including those beyond Durham would not be implausible. One other text was dismembered and reassembled into another book, Thomas de Capuway’s *Dictamen*, incorporated into the *REGISTRUM DIUERSARUM LITERARUM*, a manuscript neither digitised nor entirely catalogued, discovered within the Durham Cathedral’s archive.

²² The books registered as K, M, O, Q, R and S are not found among the digitalised works or at the Cathedral Archive under those same names. It raises the possibility of dismemberment or relocation to an alternative location. Therefore, we cannot detail and comment on them, except for the major works on them. It seems that they covered Durham’s history and its legal regiment, which may have been replaced by new works on the subject, mainly the legal texts, which may have lost their meaning due to possible changes in Durham’s jurisdiction or political position in England.

²³ On the epistolary nature and societal value of registers and charters, see Declerq 2000 and Ysebaert 2015.

²⁴ Cornelius 2010, p. 292, explains that “when assembled into collections (formularies) and appended to manuals of letter-writing (*artes dictandi*) these letters served as illustrations of correct epistolary style. Hence, a student might encounter, within the materials that taught the correct execution of secretarial duties, letters soliciting appointment to that office. He would be invited to adapt a letter between a generic ‘clerk’ and ‘bishop’ to his own purposes; the letter’s style and formulation would testify to the student’s progress and hence support the legitimacy of his petition”.

the product of letter-writing techniques learned through *Artes Dictaminis* in the previous centuries²⁵.

The oldest charters, which date back to the eleventh century, may not have followed strictly any particular *Dictamen*, which were still being developed in Italian communal cities and France²⁶. Still, they share some resemblance to the other registers. It indicates that some writing practices were somewhat standardised even before the development of the *Dictamen*²⁷. However, there are no complete studies yet on how those previous practices of writing official documents, with textual structures similar to letters, evolved from late ancient Roman bureaucratic structures to what would be the standard practice in the eleventh century.

Even though some of those works might not have been read as letters in the last centuries, nor being composed as letters, the presence of at least three *Dictamina* treatises among those eighteen books suggests that they were read by the people working and studying in the *Spendement* as of letter-writing practices. One may argue that those registers or even the charters were not letters, presenting valid arguments to sustain their opinion. Nevertheless, one cannot deny the use of letter-writing practices to produce official documents in late medieval chanceries. We cannot precisely know how many *Dictamina* there were in those eighteen books, but there were at least three: two *Summae*, one from an English Author²⁸, and one *Tractatus Dictaminis*, written there in Durham. There were likely more, but we cannot be precise about how many as we only have a few books and some unbonded texts.

As I have explained, the *Spendement* was also a classroom, and some of those books had a clear pedagogical role. However, there is a second reason to use old cartularies in a chancery: the preservation of a unique style representing Durham's chancery, recognisable in other places. Grévin (2008, p. 274) explains that “the creation of a common rhetorical language allowing medieval states to produce documents of original appearance from these places of inspiration must have depended on a combination of institutional constraints and linguistic and cultural conditioning of the

²⁵ On the evolution of the *Dictamen*, the best references are Camargo 2001; Turcan-Verkerk 2009; Witt 1982; Alessio 2001; Ward 2019.

²⁶ On epistolary styles before the *Dictamen* in England, see Griffith 2000.

²⁷ On epistolary practices before the *Dictamen* in England, see Insley 2011 and Haskett 1996.

²⁸ There is no certain information about Richard of Pophis's place of birth or where he might have studied and worked. Considering the name, he might have been English, German, or Norman.

writers. The development of techniques for formalising language in the chancery indeed implied the creation of a true stylistic habitus internalising rhetorical knowledge taught in the *studia*, adapting it to the communication and legal requirements of different institutions”²⁹. Grévin (2008, p. 276) adds that, “ars dictaminis is a rhetorical structuring technique of discourse characteristic of the late Middle Ages, creating rhythmic and metaphorical prose, conducive to the solemn expression of political power”^{30,31}.

The two *Summae Dictaminis* suggest an occasional need to search for reliable structures, prestigious excerpts from ancient and medieval writers, and direct definitions of the parts each sort of official document would have to have³². As one of them was from England, choosing treatises written by English people would positively affect the reception of those treatises in England. The author’s choice for specific textual structures, genre characteristics, proper representation of the hierarchy within a particular community, and authors who should be quoted was more reliable than other *dictatores* who may have lived in kingdoms or cities with severe political and administrative differences from England.

However, the key to correctly understanding the books in the *Spendement* is the *TD*, written by a monk named *Williamus de Waillay*, about 1400. This text is a rare case of a single and autographed copy of a work prepared to be used by Durham’s students inside Durham Cathedral³³. It is uncommon to find texts written in the same place they should be used, autographed and with so many deictic references to the place in which it

²⁹ La création d’un langage rhétorique commun permettant aux États médiévaux de produire des documents d’apparence originale à partir de ces lieux d’inspiration a dû dépendre d’une combinaison de contraintes institutionnelles et de conditionnements linguistiques et culturels des rédacteurs. L’élaboration de techniques de formalisation du langage en chancellerie impliquait en effet la création d’un véritable habitus stylistique intériorisant des savoirs rhétoriques enseignés dans les studia, mais adaptés aux exigences communicationnelles, symboliques et juridiques des différentes institutions

³⁰ L’*ars dictaminis* est une technique de structuration rhétorique du discours caractéristique du bas Moyen Âge, créant une prose rythmée et métaphorisée, favorable à l’expression solennelle du pouvoir politique.

³¹ There are few studies comparing *artes* and *summae dictaminis*. However, there are even fewer studies, if any, analysing the styles of varied chanceries in certain countries and comparing the styles in each country.

³² On the textual structure of medieval official letters, administrative offices, courts and the *Dictamen*, see GRÉVIN 2008 and MONFASANI 2008.

³³ This exemplar may not be the only one that existed. Many teachers may have written their own *Dictamen*. CORNELIUS 2010, p. 302, says that “during the second half of the fourteenth century, an internally differentiated teaching tradition of *ars dictaminis* developed in England, comparable to that observed in the French and Italian traditions, if on a considerably smaller scale. One group of teachers attempted a rapprochement with the tradition of classical rhetoric, producing manuals of *ars dictaminis* that drew heavily on twelfth-century arts of poetry and prose: another group stripped *ars dictaminis* to its formulaic essentials and taught letter-writing alongside the basic administrative skills of accounting and the drafting of legal instruments”.

was written. The other texts in the same manuscript are letter models, a concise explanation of the parts of a letter, a treatise on preaching, book IV from *Rhetorica ad Herennium*, and several excerpts from Geoffrey of Vinsauf's *Poetria Noua*. The combination of the text strongly suggests that this very book was used to teach letter-writing practices in all their complexity; the book covers the essential structure of an administrative letter, the elements of phonetics and clauses, principles of rhetoric, and epistolary models to be used as examples.³⁴

The last sentence of William of Whalley's text indicates the reason for composing the text, "*ad honorem dei trinette iste libellus pro iuuenibus exaratus*" (In the honour of the Triune God, this booklet was prepared for young people). Therefore, we can ascertain that the book was destined for young male students who used to take classes within the Cathedral. Moreover, passages like "*vt si dicatur femmina anglicana forme egregie*"³⁵ (as if it was said by an English woman outstandingly), in the second paragraph of the second part of the text, show deictic references to where it should be used - England.

The *TD* served not only as a guide to style but also as an educational tool for ensuring that future employees of the *Spendement* and other Durham houses' offices possessed strong written communication skills in both legal and diplomatic contexts. The Cathedral Priory required individuals with a deep understanding of Latin, canon law, Durham's court jurisprudence, and local history. Thus, investing in primary and higher education was not simply an act of charity but also an investment in potential personnel who would be difficult to find elsewhere. Even if Durham managed to recruit well-trained individuals, additional training in local business and legal matters would still be necessary.

4. From Antiquity to the Middle Ages: a new practice made with ancient materials

Ancient Rhetoric was adapted and integrated with other disciplines and genres, and it was accommodated in the Trivium, which sided with Logic and Grammar. It was not an isolated or purely theoretical discipline in the Middle Ages, but rather a practical and very close to the post-modern idea of interdisciplinary science. Besides the other disciplines in the Trivium, it was closely related to theology, law, poetry, and preaching.

³⁴ On the frequent use of poetry manuals, rhetoric treatises and *Dictamen*, see GRÉVIN 2015 and WARD 2001.

³⁵ A paraphrase of Isidore's sentence, in which we read "*Femina aegyptia*" (Egyptian woman), *Etymologiae* II.19.

As new legal and political systems were being formed, international diplomacy grew stronger as internal and external forces were drawing the Western European nations; they needed a display of connection and knowledge of the previous most significant political, ideological, and linguistic empire Europe knew. Moreover, most of the Catholic Hermeneutics were based on Ciceronian ideas of interpretation and discursive applications of the Latin and Greek prose filtered by the Christian Fathers, especially Augustine.

It should be noted that there is no direct connection between Cicero's Rhetoric and the late Middle Ages because the latter was built upon the ideas of Late Antiquity, not Roman Republican precepts. That is also the perception of Cox (2022, pg. 2), "Certainly, if we look to Cicero's Rome or Demosthenes's Athens for our paradigms of political rhetoric, it must be said that medieval Europe offers little that meets the prescription. General histories of rhetoric have correspondingly tended to characterize medieval Europe as overwhelmingly secondary in its rhetorical practices: focused on the textual rather than the oral, with the exception of preaching, and largely oblivious to political contexts". This fact is often overlooked but is crucial to understanding the historical context of that time. In particular, the influence of several waves of Germanic people upon late ancient Christianity in England played a significant role in shaping the ideas and culture of the late Middle Ages in the British Islands. The intellectual ferment of late Antiquity and early Middle Ages witnessed the fusion of Greco-Roman rhetorical traditions with emerging Christian theological discourse, Germanic legal and political systems, catalysing a transformative synthesis of classical and Christian rhetorical paradigms.

Ambrose, Jerome, Gregory, and Augustine exemplified the multi-faceted nature of rhetorical engagement in Late Antiquity, serving as theologians, bishops, and prolific correspondents who wielded Rhetoric as a potent instrument of persuasion and exhortation. They wrote several works on Rhetoric, such as *De Doctrina Christiana*, *De Viris Illustribus*, and *De Officiis Ministrorum*, in which they adapted the classical principles and techniques of Rhetoric to the Christian context and argued that Rhetoric was a valuable and noble art for interpreting and communicating the word of God. They used their rhetorical skills to address various topics and audiences, to convey their authority and personality, and to persuade and comove their readers. They also delivered

and recorded many public speeches, such as sermons, lectures, and polemics, which were influential in shaping the Christian identity and doctrine.

By adapting classical rhetorical techniques, such as argumentation, arrangement, and stylistic embellishment, these rhetorician-theologians endeavoured to articulate and defend the canons of the Christian faith, compellingly articulating theological truths to diverse audiences across the late ancient European world. Moreover, the epistolary genre emerged as a quintessential medium for rhetorical expression and engagement in late ancient Christianity, facilitating the exchange of theological ideas, pastoral counsel, and ecclesiastical admonition among Christian communities and ecclesiastical authorities. The rhetorical virtuosity displayed in the letters of Ambrose, Jerome, Gregory, and Augustine underscores the dynamic interplay between Rhetoric and religious authority, as these epistolary missives served as vehicles for disseminating doctrinal orthodoxy and pastoral guidance within the expanding Christian community.

Then, we are led to question what the Middle Ages was. The answer cannot be the axioms built between the Renaissance and the first half of the twentieth century through a discourse of exclusion³⁶. The Middle Ages, or *Media Aetas*, were not the “Dark Ages”, a period of barbarism, pure desire for bloodshed, and complete illiteracy, during which nothing literary or philosophical was composed. The period concerning the sixth to the fifteenth centuries cannot be resumed to the Carolingian reign, the Italian communal cities, Viking invasions, and feudal systems. In the words of Chinca and Young (2005, pg.3), “If we are to avoid giving an anachronistic picture of the Middle Ages, then both our definitions of these key terms and our conception of their interrelation require reconsideration and refinement”.

Many revolutions occurred within that timeframe, and each place in Western and Central Europe experienced and thrived differently in political, societal, and educational novelties. In particular, the Anglo-Saxon context serves as a compelling case study for exploring the dynamic evolution of rhetorical traditions within the crucible of medieval England. The successive waves of Roman, Saxon, Danish, Norse, and Norman influences engendered a rich tapestry of linguistic diversity and cultural hybridity, shaping the contours of rhetorical expression and literary production in Latin as a universal second language for all literate people in the Christian medieval world.

³⁶ On the idea of exclusion dormant in discourses and ideologies, see FOUCAULT (1971).

Albeit the process of pasteurisation and homogenisation of the Middle Ages into a small and exact temporal and geographical frame, the prejudice inherited by the Renaissance and the long-term disinterest in analysing medieval documents and in publicising medieval literary and technical works had been negatively impacting the studies on the reception and dissemination of ancient knowledge and literature in the Middle Ages. Recent efforts in revisiting Western history have been fruitful. New perceptions of the Middle Ages and what they bequeathed us have also changed how we understand Classical Antiquity.³⁷

All human thoughts and practices continuously evolved from Classical Rome to late medieval Western and Central Europe. Far from having been frozen between the sixth and fifteenth centuries, that same knowledge Augustine established upon Aristotle and Cicero's works was used to create fresh answers to recently founded societies, based not on Cicero's idea of the Republic but on the recent Roman-Christian ideas within the Germanic influence in a fragmentary societal and political organisation. Furthermore, the texts that survived in the Middle Ages were not solely chosen by medieval people: the first filters to limit the circulation or even erase from existence the ideas, texts and books written in ancient Rome and Greece existed in Antiquity. Then, some texts got lost in the early Middle Ages and then in the late Middle Ages. Therefore, late medieval people chose those works that responded to their needs and followed their beliefs³⁸, but the early Middle Ages chose the whole corpus they had, and then, the late Antiquity and so on.

Besides the authors used in schools (Cato, Theodolus, Avianus, Maximian, Claudian, Statius, Horace, Ovid, and Virgil³⁹), Cicero was the most studied and prolific author, regularly called Tullius. Constable (1992, pg. 38-8) points out that Ciceronian influence affected literary circles, international diplomacy, and prose composition in general. That influence is directly related to the rise of new political and societal organisations, mostly through the *Ars Dictaminis*⁴⁰. Established by the Benedictine monk Alberic of Montecasino by 1090, the *Dictamen* was a response to societies that needed a

³⁷ On the new studies on the Middle Ages, see Mathews (2011), Johnston and Van Dussen (2015), Jager (2019), Heng (2021), and Lazarinni (2021)

³⁸ In the words of John Ward, "If a text did not have a specific field of utilisation, it fell into obscurity." (2019, p. 351)

³⁹ On the ancient Roman authors used in schools, see Orme (2006, pg. 98-110)

⁴⁰ The best descriptions of *Ars Dictaminis* are still Turcan-Verkerk (2009) and Grévin (2015).

simple and easily recognisable set of rules to pen official documents, as exposed by Patt (1978)⁴¹

In a context where letters were used to spread philosophy, moral precepts, and communication between leaders and their communities, as the Christian Fathers did in the late Antiquity, the *Dictamen* was hardly an innovative idea. It is already known that there were letters in England in the tenth century similar to those that followed the *Dictamen* centuries later⁴². However, the *Dictamen* established the primary theoretical references, as well described by Alessio (2006, pg. 335) “It is important to recognise, first, that for the theorists of the *ars dictaminis* as for all other practitioners of medieval communication theory down to the advent of humanism, the principal sources for classical rhetorical doctrine were the *De inventione* and the *Rhetorica ad Herennium*”.

The brilliant work of Clanchy (2013) on written documents and literacy in the late Middle Ages helps us to comprehend the “response” William Patt talks about. The nature of writing underwent a significant shift towards practicality and universality during the late Middle Ages. While the most prestigious Catholic books, including the Scriptures and those works written by the Christian Fathers and Catholic saints, were yet the most abundant books found in libraries, commentaries, and glossae circulated more and more. It implies that more and more people were learning to read and write. The increasing number of schools in England and Europe in General also strengthens that perception. Individual written documents also evolved to serve more immediate practical purposes and adopted new formats, including the *Dictamen*.

Therefore, we can safely say that part of the societal and political development experienced in England was connected to ancient Rhetoric practices applied in several communication fields. That is what Grévin (2008, p. 273) states, “The development of the pre-modern Western state, from England to Bohemia, was accompanied by a recovery and adaptation of the political rhetoric developed in the administrative, political, and ideological laboratories that were the Papal States and the Hohenstaufen emperors' Sicily in the 13th century”⁴³. The rise of Modern societies in the late Middle Ages was a complex

⁴¹ On the expectations and answers of the *Dictamen*, see Patt (1978).

⁴² On the letters in England before the *Dictamen*, see Griffith (2000) and Haseldine (1994).

⁴³ Le développement de l'État occidental prémoderne, de l'Angleterre à la Bohême, s'est en effet accompagné d'une récupération et d'une adaptation de la rhétorique politique élaborée dans ces laboratoires administratifs, politiques et idéologiques que furent au XIIIe siècle l'État pontifical et la Sicile des empereurs Hohenstaufen.

evolution. Changes in the education system were possible because of changes in political and religious structures and societal expectations. However, those changes were also caused by shifts in the general mentality and literacy increase.

Integrating classical Rhetoric, Latin Grammar, and secular literature into the educational curriculum underscores the enduring legacy of rhetorical traditions in shaping new political and societal institutions and modelling an English cultural identity. The youngest students tackled Latin grammar, poetical metrics and rhythm, and more advanced ones focused on rhetorical theory, poetry and prose composition, Logic, and Hermeneutics. These last two were very close to their understanding of Rhetoric. Even though few medieval authors became indispensable when studying Latin, such as Marbodius of Rennes and Geoffrey of Vinsauf, students and their masters drew inspiration from the rhetorical techniques of ancient Roman orators and philosophers. Logically, the Christian authors and their influence, namely Cicero and Quintilian, were abundantly copied and read.

The study of rhetoric sharpened students' rhetorical skills and imbued them with the ability to compose and recognise several sorts of documents, most of which were in an epistolary format. Thus, the pedagogical incorporation of ancient Rhetoric laid the groundwork for cultivating what would become the late epistolary culture, the *Dictamen*. Letter-writing was then the basis for institutional communication and philosophical treatises, following Horace, Paul the Apostle, Seneca, Jerome, Ambrose, Augustine, and Gregory the Great. Therefore, mastering writing and interpreting letters became a societal requirement for a significant number of job positions within and outside the Church. Cornelius (2010, pg. 298) clarifies, "The ostensible purpose of such instruction was to ensure that the letter proceeded in a manner appropriate to its circumstances and hence to maximise the sender's chances of receiving favourable hearing. However, the specifically codified form taken by this instruction lent the instruction a slightly different function: by providing a menu of ready-made and approved formulas, the *ars dictaminis* spared chancery clerks and notaries from the task of making independent judgments concerning matters of social decorum".

However, the development of the dictaminal culture dialogues more with the idea of an orator, as Cicero puts it in the *De Oratore*, than just people applying rules and inserting quotations mindlessly, as commonly thought. The list of books catalogued by Fyshburn in 1421 within the *Spendement* shows us that to work in a chancery, knowing

the basics of rhetorical figures, the parts of an oration, and a few quotations drawn from *Flores Rhetorici* was far from the minimum requirement. Scribes, dictatores, and most people, if not all of them, should also have knowledge of Canon Law, Civil Law, royal and local jurisprudence, local and national history, and Hermeneutics.

In sum, as Grévin (2012, p.186-7) explained, “The nature of the exercise indeed demands a bewildering language virtuosity, and one must extract the meaning from its rhetorical matrix to analyse it. However, this text speaks volumes about the ideology of the dictamen and its practical applications. It fits into a trilogy that praises the arts of the trivium. Grammar and dialectic thus frame rhetoric, which dominates them. (...) The practical utility of rhetoric - including an instructive comparison between bad rhetorician lawyers and theatre actors - and especially the final appeal indicates the purpose of teaching aimed at training notaries, lawyers, and judges”⁴⁴.

There are few studies, if any, on a profound analysis of the documents produced in the dictaminal way. Most documents, when analysed, did not consider fundamental characteristics. First, all documents were produced to be read out loud at some point since medieval societies had a different approach to reading and consuming books. Second, the written production and the spread of books had different values and technological limits than we are used to, and those differences are crucial to understanding what and how they write and read. Third, as proposed by Foucault (1971), each document was a dispute between the sender and the addressee. This dispute occurs in the literate struggle of who knows better the models, ancient and contemporary authors, quotations, and how to apply rhetorical and poetic elements in prose. Lastly, the concept we have of a higher and pleasing speech or letter is from the expectation they have in the Middle Ages. Novelties (or appearances of novelty) were not as highly valued as we do. Late medieval people appreciated more a display of vast erudition on matters that his audience was also literate than avid consumers of new ideas, genres, and mediums.

We cannot yet investigate the product of the *Dictamen* and the classical Rhetoric in the late Middle Ages due to the edition of cartularies, letters, documents, speeches, and more studies about them. To overcome that shortness of comprehension, we are going to examine the pedagogical source to produce those documents, the *TD*. The first question

⁴⁴ L'utilité pratique de la rhétorique – incluant une instructive comparaison entre les avocats mauvais rhétoriciens et les acteurs de théâtre 39 – et surtout l'appel final indiquent le but d'un enseignement destiné à former les notaires, les avocats et les juges du royaume de Bohême. (p. 186-7)

is who *Williemus de Wayllay* could be. The primary source of his identity is the autographed text, which only says he is *monachus eisdem*. Therefore, he was a monk in Whalley and then in Durham.

The greatest source to people at Durham's Cathedral during the Middle Ages is the Durham *Liber Vitae*, an extensive compilation of official and non-official records on relevant people in Durham between the 10th and 16th centuries. However, there is no entry of any *Williemus de Wayllay* nor any reference to *Wayllay*. Investigating the origin of the word, we come to two possibilities: a) most likely, William was a monk in the church of Whalley, a very small provenance in Lancashire; b) less likely, William is Welsh, if we understand *Wayllay* as a corruption of *Walais*, or, in modern English, Wales⁴⁵. As the MS was written under the supervision of Richard of Lancashire, William may have been brought by Richard to help improve Durham's Chancellery. Regardless, his origin is a poor and small community.

Some elements throughout William's letter-writing treatise indicate some feelings of English patriotism. The passage "*vt si dicatur femmina anglicana forme egregie,*" in the second paragraph of *Causam Secudam*, shows a paraphrase of an Isidore sentence, in which we read "*feminae aegyptia*"⁴⁶. The whole passage is, in fact, a quotation from Isidore, besides the word *anglicana*, used in place of *aegyptia*. The preference for the local deictic reference seems to fit well the building of a local educational context.

The work has 20 pages (10 parchment folios front and verse). The *incipit*, an emphasised title in red ink at the top of page 90R, reads *Incipit quidam Tractatus Dictaminis* (starts here a treatise on Composition). On the bottom of page 100R, the closing names the author in a separate line that reads *Istum tractatum edidit dominus Williamus de Wayllay, Monachus eiusdem* (Mr William of Whalley, monk here, edited this treatise). There is no artistic work; the pages are crude and display only the text and comments from a third party at the side of the pages. The comments suggest a pedagogical use, as they refer to keywords, related sentences and works, minor corrections, and so on. The red ink stops at page 91R. Between pages 91R and 100F, stressed words and

⁴⁵ David and Lynda Rollason, *The British Library*, London, 2007, vol I, II, III. Vol. II, pg. 347 points out to *Walais* as an Anglo-French surname to "welsh". Vol III. Pg. 583 refers to a William of *Walais* or William le *Weleis* as a person to whom the land was granted in Brompton-on-Swale, Yorkshire, and subsequently passed the land to Easby Abbey in 1155. Indeed not William of *Wayllay*, who knew the work of Geoffrey of *Vinsauf* and *Marbodus*, who lived after 1155.

⁴⁶ Isidore, *Etymologiae* II.19

corrections were done using brown ink. It indicates the manuscript was not produced in a wealthy scribe centre, nor was it composed to display wealth.

The rubricator divided the work into eight sections, following notations on the side of the pages. Some sections are just a few lines, like the first one; others are as long as half of the work, like the fifth section. The work presents the following division:

	Page	Subject ⁴⁷
Causam Primam	90R	Introduction
C. Secundam	90R	Phonetics Outlines
C. Tertiam	90V	Metrics
C. Quartam	91R	Dactyl and Spondee in clauses
C. Quintam	91V	<i>Rhetorici Flores</i>
C. Sextam	97V	What are polished sentences
C. Septimam	99R	How to adorn sentences
C. Octauam	99V	The order within sentences

5. DOCERE

To narrow our investigation further, we will target a few practical application examples following the rhetorical triad established by Cicero, the “*Docere, Mouere, Delectare*”. In the very first lines of the *TD*, we have a direct connection with Ciceronian texts and precepts, as it reads: *Ad quid valeat dictare enarrat Tullius, dicens nichil fere prestabilius quam dicendi tenere mentes hominum, impellere quo voluntates vnum velut deducere. Virtus in oracionis dictate illum tenet ad quem dirigitur ut petitionem diligenter attendat. Allicit vt petenti consenciens adquiescat. Impellit vt quod postulatur faciat. Deducit et ad hoc vsque deflectur vt propriis rebus ea que sunt aliterius anteponat.* (Tullius explains the purpose of composing speeches, saying that there is almost nothing more valuable than holding people's minds in speaking, compelling their wills as if

⁴⁷ I gave the names here. Some sections have a headline, but some do not.

leading them to one goal. The power of composing speeches keeps the person to whom it is directed attentive to the request. It entices so that the one requesting agrees and consents. It compels so that what is demanded is done. It leads and, to this extent, deviates so that the person prioritises the interests of others over their own affairs.)

Cicero's triad emphasises the fundamental principle of *Docere* (to teach), which forms the foundation of effective communication. The concept underscores the importance of imparting knowledge and information to the audience in a way that fosters understanding and enlightenment. To fulfil the role of a teacher or communicator, the speech or official document⁴⁸ must have an in-depth knowledge of the subject matter, which requires extensive research and preparation. They must be capable of simplifying complex ideas into digestible information, making it accessible to the audience without losing the essence of the information.⁴⁹

At first, it is mandatory to establish credibility. There is a Cicero's indirect quotation in the *TD* alerting about it: "*Tullius in libro de paradoxis verborum sonitus optimorum atque ornatissimorum inanis est nulla subiecta sententia nec scientiarum exornatio ut dicit. Idem in rethoricis est que non verbis sed in ipsis rebus.* (As Tullius says in the book of paradoxes, the sound of the best and most ornate words is empty when the given sentence and the embellishment is dull. The same is in rhetoric, which is not in words but in the very matters)". Albeit the incompleteness of the quotation, we learn that without the recognition of knowledge and the perception of authority, even the most beautiful words and most well adorned sentences are worthless.

However, to establish the authority and demonstrate knowledge varies. The societal spheres in which Rhetoric was applied in the Middle Ages are utterly different in essence and format from those that Cicero knew in his times. In the Middle Ages, Rhetoric was applied in Diplomacy, official communication between two groups inside the same institution (e.g. Priors of different orders within the Catholic Church), few cases in local courts, even fewer in royal courts, and some scholarly disputes of Scriptures' interpretation. There is no Forum; there is no Senate House⁵⁰. Similarly, the target

⁴⁸ I have chosen to use "speech or official document" instead of the orator's figure because the document spoke more in the Middle Ages than the one who wrote it and read it in public. The chancery or office is the ultimate author, not a specific person.

⁴⁹ On the concept of Societal Spheres, see Volochinov (1977).

⁵⁰ Cox (2022) collected a series of studies and medieval books showing that political speech in Parliament was already present in the late Middle Ages. It suggests that the reception and practical application of ancient Rhetoric might have been even more comprehensive and vast than previously thought.

audience cannot be compared. On the one hand, the medieval people were more plural within a bigger societal spectrum than the Patricians in ancient Rome. Knights and lay people that could be *litterati* or *illiterati* – which does not infer that they knew to read or not, but, rather, if they were at some point members of the church or not – aristocrats, clergy, and even people from abroad. Therefore, the rhetorical approach to build credibility cannot be the same.

The crucial point is that the source of the truth in written documents for Western European people from late Antiquity until the Modern Times is almost exclusively the Catholic God⁵¹. In Cicero's time the truth was built, and it could come from several sources, depending on the ability of its crafter. In that sense, any person could build his own truth and convince people of that truth that he taught. In the Catholic world, contrarywise, the truth always comes from divine sources: God, Angels, and Prophets. Ordinary people are not the source of any truth in that scenario. The scribes, dictators, philosophers, lawyers, and others who did their jobs through words should convince people that they hold the correct interpretation of God's will – which can be even more challenging than crafting the truth about a given matter.

When composing speeches or official documents, scribes and dictators needed to create a balance between connecting with the sacredness and authority of the divine message and making it accessible to a diverse audience. This is where Cicero's lessons on Rhetoric comes in, giving the right tools to persuade and edify an audience while guiding them towards a deeper understanding of divine precepts. To achieve that balance, speeches and official documents must blend authoritative delivery with clarity and connection to scripture or other Christian texts while also ensuring accessibility to resonate with various societal fields.

As a chancery of a Benedictine Priory, the *Spendement* could erect its image of authority and reliability within the Catholic world. To strengthen that image, Durham invested in Education much more than most of the Cathedrals and Priories in England⁵². First, Northumbrian boys were sent to Grammar and Song schools. Then, the most prominent students were selected to have *Dictamen*, Rhetoric, Canon and Civil Law, and History classes in the *Spendement*⁵³. Lastly, the elevated number of Cicero's works in

⁵¹ Pagans, Jews, Scandinavians and other people would not have the chance to argument and defend their faiths and beliefs in written documents.

⁵² On the number invested in Durham, see Orme (2015).

⁵³ This is narrated by Durham's Rituals. See Claxton (2020).

Durham⁵⁴ unveils Durham's concern with the significance theoretical knowledge and its representation had among other chanceries and offices⁵⁵.

This strategy allowed Durham Cathedral Priory to prepare local people to work in a chancery in which local matters were much more frequent than continental issues. The *Spendement* hired boys and men trained within the corridors of the Cathedral, trained by trustful masters and teachers – which could include monks who studied in Oxford, where Durham had a house since the later thirteenth century –and also used the local knowledge to ease the studies on local jurisprudence and general ideology. Thus, the image of Durham's Prior and his chancery was stable and reliable.

Docere in the Middle Ages also relied on the construction of Collective Memories, as in ancient Rome. Maurice Halbwachs (1968) defines Collective Memory as defining a social group, justifying its congregation and demonstrating its temporal and spatial limits. In other words, it is a set of ideological elements justified by shared memories that mark the present space of the group, even though it is not limited to an exact temporal delineation. Furthermore, it enables them to recognise themselves as equals before the institutions that regulate their existence.

The Collective Memory becomes the truth that guides a group, defining its existence and sustaining it as long as it persists. A speech or an official document could not deny various Collective Memories, especially those related to religion. However, as most of the societal and political institutions were new, including Civil Law and Local courts, speeches and official documents helped to shape the idea of Civil Rights and Legal Systems. Hence, the Collective Memories related to societal and legal matters were arbitrarily designed using rhetorical elements, becoming the truth that reveals the new

⁵⁴ According to Surtees (1938, there were at least 40 Cicero's books in Durham throughout the late Middle Ages. Not all manuscripts are described, but there are some works named among them: *De Amicitia*, *De Inventione*, *Rhetorica Ad Herennium* (believed to have been written by Cicero), *Paradoxa Stoicorum*, *De Legibus*, *Somnium Scipionis*, *De Senectute*, *De Officiis*. There are also a few entries named *Rhetorica Tulli* and *Tullius De Eloquentia*, which did not survive, but, probably are related to the *Oratore* since in the TD references to *De Oratore* are called *De Eloquentia* or *Paradoxa Verba*.

⁵⁵ Grévin (2012, p. 177) tells that “Contrary to Cicero's rhetoric, which was tendentially confined to its role as theoretical authority, the *ars dictaminis* was intended to address concrete needs. Moreover, the two levels complemented each other more than they opposed each other. The teaching of dictamen, less abstract than that of Cicero's treatises, served as a propaedeutic for the career of practitioners of authoritative languages. (À l'opposé de la rhétorique cicéronienne, tendanciellement confinée dans son rôle d'autorité théorique, l'*ars dictaminis* était destiné à couvrir des besoins concrets. Les deux niveaux se complétaient d'ailleurs plus qu'ils ne s'opposaient. L'enseignement du dictamen, moins abstrait que celui des traités cicéroniens, servait de propédeutique à la carrière des praticiens des langages de l'autorité) ». Hence, to have and to quote a considerable number of Cicero's works would bring Durham the solidness needed to be respected in the international context.

dominant groups through forgetting what came before, even if it entails the prior non-existence of groups with similar characteristics.

In these cases, the death of the past was necessary to create these new Collective Memories, which, in turn, would rely upon a brand-new past. To interpret or reinterpret the sole truth from the Christian God meant to reshape or even destroy a previous Collective Memory. It means that speeches and official documents were prepared not only to convince but also to delete, when necessary, the basis of the other party. All sides should follow the Catholic doctrines (even if they were not Christians, such as the Scandinavians or the Jews, of whom there is vast documentation in legal courts in medieval England⁵⁶). This continuous ideological confront was not particularly traumatic because several shifts in all societies' fields were also changing. Even though the source of truth was (almost) invariable, the Christian God, to convince others that one's interpretations were superior or more reliable, led to theoretical and practical discussions about the format of those new societal, political, and legal institutions and how they would serve the truth of God. In that fashion, speeches and official documents explored changing the lights, or Collective Memories, surrounding the matters it is concerned with.

Nonetheless, the audience was more likely to be persuaded if they perceived the speech or official document, or the figure represented through them, as an authority on the subject, not only in its surroundings. All institutions and their representatives with power and voice to compose a document or speech were indeed Christian men at the time, so they would be equalled in that concern⁵⁷. Hence, the wanted credibility is not just about qualifications, experience, or connection to the Christian God (which were mandatory, not optional) but also about the ability to communicate effectively. A credible document or speech must display the credibility of the institution or person it represents, making the audience more receptive to its message. In Durham's case, the documents and speeches written in the *Spendement* should match the position Durham had in England's multicultural and borderless scenario as a lighthouse for England's international Diplomacy, a harbour of Classical Studies, and one of the few centres of conversion of heathen in the British Islands.

⁵⁶ Clanchy (2013) uses several documents about Jews to show how non-Christians were treated in medieval England.

⁵⁷ It was a mechanism of exclusion, *de facto*.

A few things should gather the audience's attention. Certainly, the first element that would draw attention would be the sound of the words and the sentences, followed by the position or order of the words and possible quotations. The *TD* explains this with the following words: *Postquam dictum est de situ necnon et ordinacone verborum de ipsorum ornatu restat aliqua littera vnum tangendum vnum notandum est. Primo quod a Tullio traduntur quidam flores rethorici quibus numero modo vernantibus decor eloquii venunstatur.* (After discussing the arrangement and order of words, as well as their embellishment, there remains one letter which must not be touched upon. Firstly, it should be noted that Tullius handed down certain rhetorical flowers, by the enumeration of which the charm of eloquence flourishes). The rhetorical flower, in that sense, is any element or tool used to achieve the proposed objectives. To speak correctly, display knowledge of Latin phonetics and rhythm, and the ability to rearrange words and sentences to build new meanings brings the aura of erudition and correctness. It would give authority to the speech or official document when composed and read correctly.

To inform becomes more than just telling a story or narrating a fact. *Docere* represents more than the exposition or construction of the *Materiae*⁵⁸. It equally depends on the matter to be told and the exploration of diverse ways of speaking the same thing. That is also taught in the *TD*, when it quotes Quintilian: *dicit orator Quintilliannus, non est desperandum hiis quae dicta sunt, aliquid melius posse reperiri, neque eum adeo pauperem et ieunam natura facit eloquenciam vt vna de re dici bene nisi semel non possit.* (Quintilian, the orator, states that repetition should not lead to despair regarding what has been said, as something better may yet be found, nor does it make eloquence so impoverished and meagre that one cannot speak well on a subject more than once).

Following Marbode's and Vinsaulf's interpretation of Cicero's works, the *TD* lists several rhetorical figures to be used in order to rearrange words, sentences, attributing new meaning to ideas, examples, memories: *Conversio, Complexio, Traduccio, Sinonima, Contencio, Exclamacio, Raciocinacio, Sentencia, Articulus, Similiter Cadens, Similiter Desinens, Annonimacio, Gradacio, Definicio, Transicio, Correcio, Ocupacio, Disiuncchio, Conuinccio, Adiuncchio, Conduplicacio, Subieccio, Dubitacio, Descripcio, Circumlocucio, Digressio, Interpretacio, Permissio, Distribucio, Diminucio, Diuisio, Contencio, Similitudo, and Significacio.* The section "*Rhetorici Flores*", in which these

⁵⁸ Or *materie* in medieval Latin, due to a contraction of the diphthong "ae".

figures are explained and exemplified, represents more than half of the work, indicating its relevance.

Therefore, the matter to be sustained can be exposed in so many ways that it can be taught to one single audience several times, if necessary. A speech or an official document must be written so that the lights, shadows, contours, and corners of a given issue tell the audience as much as, or even more than, the issue itself. Even solidified ideas could be twisted and reinterpreted if the speech or official document was well penned.

6. DELECTARE

Most of the figures recommended in the *TD* reinforce another leg of Cicero's triad, the *Delectare*. It underscores the importance of engaging the audience's emotions and interests to maintain their attention and enhance the impact of a speech or document. By incorporating humour, irony, and storytelling elements, *Delectare* intends to effectively engage listeners and keep them interested in the message. We could say that while *Docere* focuses on the mind, *Delectare* is all about the spirit.

In the Middle Ages, the phonetic elements played a significant role in pleasing the audience since the speeches and official documents should be read aloud. The *TD* brings at least three sections about the sound: *causam secundam*, *tertiam*, and *quartam*. At the opening of *causam secundam*, the *TD* explains: "*Quondam turpis sonus est quam vocales occurrendo sibi se collidunt adinuicem. Et faciunt turpem sonum et hiantem. Ideo ne vocalis ad vocalem sequatur contigua quantis partis fieri deuitetur et cetera. Similiter ex occasione rixosa consonantium constituitur. Vox indistincta ac pro hoc impedit intelligem vt in isto exemplo « pro utroque vinco vobis supplico amice » Hic, reuerentia ex occasione consonantium ad se quasi rixosa sonoritas resultat in pronunciando et audientibus vox indistincta redditur*". (Occasionally, an ugly sound occurs when vowels collide with each other. They produce an unpleasant and gaping sound. Therefore, one vowel should not follow another contiguous one to avoid how it can be divided into parts, etc. Similarly, an indistinct sound is formed from the conflicting incident of consonants, and, for this reason, it hinders understanding, as in this example, "I beg you for both, my friend". Here, due to the discordant occasion of consonants, a sort of contentious sonority results in pronunciation, and the voice becomes indistinct to the listeners).

In this passage, it becomes clear that the most insignificant details for a post-modern reader could be a terrible mistake to medieval people⁵⁹. The mere encounter of two S (vobiS Supplico) and the unintended repletion of a V/U (Vinco Vobis) could harm the audience's ear and cause them to lose engagement. We fail consistently in perceiving these elements because we are not trained or used to listening to Latin, and our approach to official communication is based on written texts. Examples with vowels and other consonants also are listed and discussed in the *DT*. A simple letter of recommendation to a young monk going to Oxford sounds completely flat and disinteresting to us, but for trained years in the Middle Ages, it would sound like an orchestra if well-composed.

However, the most brilliant example is the *Prosimetrum* or the use of poetic structures in prose composition. Turcan-Verkerk (2003, p. 111) defines *Prosimetrum* as “one of his innovations regarding traditional rhetoric that knew prose and metric genres is the notion of *genus mixtum*, which, with hesitations (we will return to this in a moment), then receives the name of prosimetrum, a term that we see appearing for the first time in Latin literature”⁶⁰.

Even though most of the works do not use the name “prosimetrum”, it is clear the idea of mixing verses and prose. In the *TD* we have: “*DE VERSUM SEU DISTICCONUM INICIIS TRIANCONIBUS ET CISSURIS. In primis notandum est quod versus non est incipiendus a dactalo vt diccone polisaba cuius penultima breuietur. Hiis est similibus exceptis: quam, igitur, itaque, ceterum, praeterea, verumtamen que sepius conueniunt versibus inchoandis. Item cum praecedens distincco in dactalum tertiari uideatur sequens a nullo dactalo nisi ab hac diccone quatenus inchoetur. Item non ab uno spondeo terminum reputo clausulam inchoandam. Sed a pluribus vt a duplicato spondeo.* (ON VERSE, OR ON INITIAL DISTICHES, TRIADS AND CAESURAS. First, it should be noted that a verse is not to be started with a dactyl, like in a dactylic hexameter whose penultimate syllable is shortened. This applies similarly to words such as *quam, igitur, itaque, ceterum, praeterea, and verumtamen*, often used to begin verses. Also, when the

⁵⁹ Medieval children would learn to recognise sounds and to reproduce sounds before knowing their meaning. Even though it seems inappropriate or inaccurate for us, according to Clanchy (2011, pg. 19), “‘Reading’ in this context meant pronouncing the words correctly; at this initial stage of instruction the Latin texts did not need to be understood by the reader. ‘A boy first learns the alphabet, secondly to form syllables (*sillabicare*), thirdly to read (*legere*) and fourthly to understand (*intelligere*). At each of these stages he has his own distinct sense of the purpose of that particular step”

⁶⁰ L'une de ses innovations à l'égard d'une rhétorique traditionnelle qui connaissait les genres prosaïque et métrique est la notion de *genus mixtum*, qui, avec des hésitations (nous y reviendrons dans un instant), reçoit alors le nom de *prosimetrum*, terme que nous voyons apparaître pour la première fois dans la littérature latine.

preceding caesura appears to be in a dactyl triad, the following does not start with any dactyl except for this specific case, as far as it commences with this word. Furthermore, I do not consider a clause to be commenced from a single spondee at the end. Instead, it should be commenced from several, such as from a doubled spondee).

The text refers to the application of metric rules to prose in the form of "verses". During the Middle Ages, people who worked in chanceries and courts were able to write and distinguish by ear such artful prose, which was a combination of metric and rhythm in prose composition⁶¹. Unfortunately, today, we are no longer capable of recognising the intricate nature of this form of writing due to the loss of the skills and awareness required to appreciate it. As a result, we failed to comprehend the real nature of the medieval composition, labelling it as "boring", "tedious", or even "insignificant" – a consequence of our ignorance, not theirs.

Turcan-Verkerk (2003, pg. 138) draws attention to the purposeful use of the *prosimetrum* to achieve the *Delectare*: "It seems to me that this presentation, with its precise mention of *delectatio*, corresponds exactly to many texts which, in moments of acme (cf. *quandoque*, which were already found in Henricus Francigena), are written in a poetic prose intended to touch the reader or listener"⁶². The effect *prosimetrum* would cause may have two sides: first, the sound effects caused by known rhythms and cadences at the ending of every sentence would bring joy since most people would learn in school or private classes to enjoy a certain pattern and not others; second, the recognition itself would appraise the hearing audience, as it would confirm that they were learned and able to identify phonetic and poetic elements.

The *prosimetrum* became popular, and every manual for composition would explain it, even if in a few lines. Its popularity is directly related to the increasing number of schools, teachers, and masters available at that time. The *prosimetrum* was designed so that it could be easily repeated with any matter or even repeat any matter in a separate way. Even if some people in the audience did not understand every word or sentence, they were learned enough to perceive the rhythm and judge whether it was at least acceptable or not. Furthermore, the ability to recognise the rhythmic patterns of the

⁶¹ Similar use of rhythm in the prose was attested in Pliny's letters. See Whitton (2012). It suggests that in the Roman Empire it could be a feature already.

⁶² Il me semble que cette présentation, avec sa mention précise de la *delectatio*, correspond exactement à nombre de textes qui, dans les moments d'acmé (cf. *quandoque*, que l'on trouvait déjà chez Henricus Francigena), sont écrits dans une prose poétique destinée à toucher le lecteur ou l'auditeur.

prosimetrum was not limited to the learned people alone. People now tell if a song has a recognisable rhythmic pattern (e.g., any Brazilian person will identify the rhythm of Samba Schools, or any North American would detect Country patterns in a song). They may not have studied music at all, but they can say if they knew that pattern, or if they heard it previously, and, most of all, if they like it. This process is likely to have happened with medieval people when they listened to some speaker reading a letter, a speech, or any sort of document in a public square, court, Cathedral, or even at schools. Therefore, the *prosimetrum* was a literary form designed to appeal to a broad audience in medieval times. Its success was largely due to its ability to combine both prose and poetry in a way that was easy to recognise and repeat with any matter.

Side to side with the *prosimetrum* is the metaphorical aspect of the medieval prose. According to Camargo (1992, pg. 162), “Moreover, in its intensive use of classical authors and its emphasis on stylistic ornament (more than half of the treatise is concerned with metaphor), it embodies with particular clarity the fusion of rhetoric and grammar that was to characterise the so-called ‘French style’ of *dictamen*”. In the *TD* the necessity of talking about one matter by discussing other issues are also highlighted: “*Digredimur etiam a materia ad aliud extra materias, quando scilicet inducimus comparationes sine similitudines ut eas aptemus materie. Exemplum Ovidius: Quam platanus vino gaudet, quam populus unda. Et quam limosa canna polusteis humo. Tam Venus ocia amat/ finem qui querit amoris. Cedit amor rebus, res, age tutus eris. Infinita veniuntur exempla comparacionem in auctoritati auctoribus*”. (We also digress from the subject to other topics outside of the subject matter when we introduce comparisons without similarities, in order to adapt them to the subject matter. For example, Ovid: "How the plane tree delights in wine, how the poplar in water. And how the reed in muddy soil becomes dusty. So, Venus loves idleness, who seeks the end of love: love yields to circumstances; manage your affairs, and you will be safe." Infinite examples of comparison come from authoritative authors).

In situations where complex and difficult topics are being discussed, it can be helpful to use examples that are familiar to the audience. Even if the examples used through metaphors or metonymy are seemingly unrelated, they can offer a clear and tangible explanation for the challenging topic. This can be especially useful in transitioning the audience from a state of confusion and lack of understanding to a familiar and easily comprehensible allegory. By doing so, the audience can derive a sense

of enjoyment and satisfaction, further strengthening their connection to the issue or concept being presented in the speech or official document.

The use of examples and parables is one of the pillars of the Christian tradition. It derives, as remembered by Eden (1987, pg. 72-75), from Aristotle and Cicero's lessons on Rhetoric. Even though Augustine tried to condemn the indiscriminate use of metaphors (Eden, idem, pg. 77-81), the application of *ambiguae sententiae* and *obscurae notae* in speeches and official documents increased in the Middle Ages. They were compared to the mysteries, prophecies, and confusing words of God, who talks in a way Humanity could not understand clearly. However, as the TD preaches, bringing examples from classical literature would gather the benevolence and the will of those who could identify the verses of a Roman poet or a passage of a Roman prose writer. It would create an identification with the one represented by the speech or official document. Even more, it would put them, audience members, at the same level of erudition as the well-trained and literate workers of a chancery or similar offices.

7. MOVERE

When the spirit is ablaze, the heart is fast and fiercely beating. If a speech or official document brings joy to its audience, it is likely to comove them as well. To *Mouere* an audience involves understanding their values, beliefs, and concerns. The speech or official document must be able to empathise with the audience, convincing them that their perspective and expectations are shared by the institution it represents. Building bridges through Collective Memories and known examples allows the speech or official document to frame their message in a way that resonates with the audience and speaks to their hopes and fears. Storytelling was a great approach to do it effectively. A well-told story can transport the audience to another world, make them feel the joys and sorrows proposed by the speech or official document, inspiring them to action. In the *TD*, we have a sentence that resumes the idea of *Mouere* in the following words: "*Necesse est auditore animum commoueri cum grauitas peroris dicti renouatur necesse est pretacione verborum.* (The listener's mind must be moved when the seriousness of the spoken word is renewed; it is necessary through the presentation of words)."

Even though there are specific orientations on how to use rhetorical figures to create storytelling and comove the audience in the *TD*, a loose folio (111F) just after the *TD* concentrates the information about storytelling and where it should be done in the

document: *Sciendum est primo quando in littera plena et perfecta consistiuit q unique clausule quarum prima dicitur "Exordium", commendacio, vel salutacio. Secundum "Narracio", eciam, peticio cum diuisione. Quarta "Confirmacio", sequenti concuslione. Quinta: "Subsalutacio", aliquem descendens a conclusione.* (First, it should be noted that there are five clauses in a complete and perfect letter, the first of which is called "Exordium," which serves as an introduction, commendation, or greeting. The second is "Narratio," which includes the request with its divisions. The fourth is "Confirmatio," followed by a conclusion. The fifth is "Subsalutatio," which is someone's response descending from the conclusion.)

We learned that there is a proper place to create the storytelling, the part named *Narratio*. In this section, the writer (probably also William of Whalley) says: "*Et sciendum est id si dicens mandet immoribus subiectis suis, tunc non est ponenda. Narracio in littera quia Narratio fit in littera vt declaret causas direccionis littere*". (And it should be understood that if, when speaking, one commands with immoral subjects, then it should not be included in the letter's narration, because the narration in a letter is made to clarify the reasons for the letter's direction)". In other words, the speech or official document should bring morally honourable issues to avoid conflict of interest or ethical disagreement with the audience. So much is done by those who do not hinder.

Then, it is exposed the essential information required in a good speech or official document are listed: "*Habemus tuto de narracio et qualiter in commendacione quis debet amicorum commendare virtutes. Superest ut de Peticionus aliqua dicamus Vnde sciendum est quid sepius incipit peticio ista forte. Cum principium Narracionis incipiat cum demonstracione et Nouerit vestra societas promanda vt vestram amicitiam capio non latere, vel amicitie vestre cupio fore notum et cetera. Tunc incipies coniter Peticionem per hunc modum Qua propter, qua de causa, qua de re, quare.* (We have already covered narration and how one should commend the virtues of friends in commendation. It remains for us to say something about the petitions. It is to be known what often begins this petition. Since the beginning of the narration begins with a demonstration: "May your society know to promote that I do not want your friendship to be hidden", or "I desire your friendship to be known", and so on. Then, you will begin your petition this way: Therefore, for what reason, on what account, for what cause, and why).

We first perceive the necessity of building bridges between the sides involved in the communication process. Throughout the *TD* the examples used are always based on the vocative *amice*, and using the second person in the plural, showing respect – a requirement *sine qua non*. *Mouere* consists of creating connections with the audience, whether real connections or made-up ones. Establishing bridges was taught as a mandatory strategy to make the audience feel seen and understood, welcoming the institution represented by a speech or official document as an equal to them. It makes the audience more receptive to the message. It also makes the communication process more enjoyable for the audience, which can help to hold their attention and make the message more memorable.

We learn from the *TD* that, “*Vt si ceptum fuerat, supplicat intermittere ad quid tamen optimendum non tantum politis sermonibus sed exquisitis affectum perurgentibus ordinatis periter et ornatis vti videtur vtile. Huic videtur Oracius consentire in Arte Poetica, sic dicendo: “Non satis est pulchra poemata sumpto, sed quocumque voles animum auditoris agendo”*. Igitur ad ornatum sententiarum paucos de Tullianis floribus quos in ultimo rethorice sue ponit subdam breuiter cum exemplis. (To make sure, if the intent has been set, it pleads for an interruption to what, however, is not only to be improved with polished words, but also with exquisite sentiments pressing through, arranged methodically, and adorned skillfully, it seems useful. To this, Horace appears to consent in his Art of Poetry, saying thus: ‘It is not enough to have taken fine poems, but by whatever means you wish, you must move the mind of the audience.’ Therefore, for the adornment of sentences, I will briefly present a few of the Tullian flowers which he places in his last rhetoric, with examples).”

Communication was then a complex and nuanced process that varied greatly depending on the audience and the message being conveyed. To comove the audience, it is mandatory to create a discourse that can hit that exact audience in the heart. While the Christian God and their representatives were considered omniscient and almighty within a Benedictine Priory, such as Durham, the other elements involved in the communication process were subject to variation based on the intended audience. For example, a letter of rights given to a Lord in Northumbria could not use the same language and tone used in a letter addressing a Knight in Wessex or a representative of the Benedictine order in Montecasino. Each audience in each societal sphere had their triggers to be turned on. If

misinterpreted by the scribe or dictator, the speech or official document would not cause the wanted commotion; it would cause the wrong feeling or indifference.

Furthermore, the approach taken would also depend on the purpose of the message. If the letter was requesting more financial support from landlords in the Tyne and Wear area, the approach would be different than if it were requesting more books from the Naples or Paris merchants. Despite these differences, all communication in this era was rooted in the medieval Catholic ideas of Love and Empathy, even if it was sometimes exaggeratedly passionate or cheesy. This approach was frequently based on the ethical preachings found in the New Testament and the writings of Christian Fathers and was considered a central aspect of medieval communication.

In the *TD*, we have sparse examples in a few of the rhetorical figures, such as: “*conduplicacio est cum ratione amplificationis vt imperaconis fit vnus verbi vt multorum iteracio, talis modo: Commoueri misericordia debetis pie patre erga filium lacrimantem, pedes vestros fletibus irrigantem pie patre debetis misericordia commoueri.* (Conduplicatio is a kind of amplification whereby a single word is repeated multiple times for emphasis,” as follows: “You ought to be moved by compassion for the pious father towards his weeping son, soaking your feet with tears. You ought to be moved by compassion for the pious father towards his weeping son).”. Using another rhetorical figure, *raciocinacio*, there is the following example: “*Quia nulla facilius ad id maleficium causa quam turpis amor et intemperans libido commouere potuit* (Because no cause could more easily incite to that wrongdoing than filthy love and unbridled desire.)”

The application of some rhetorical figures to cause commotion depended on the delivery of the message. *Mouere* could not be in the beginning, as the bridges between the parties were not yet established, but mainly in the middle section, where the *narratio* takes place, and in the end. At the beginning of the speech or official document, some neutrality is expected or depending on the hierarchy proposed by the use of titles and adjectives in the opening, some sense of closeness. Still, that feeling must be broken, as well explained in the *TD*: *Necesse est auditore animum commoueri cum grauitas peroris dicti renouatur necesse est pretacione verborum.* (It is necessary for the listener's mind to be shaken when the seriousness of the spoken word is renewed; it is necessary through the presentation of words).

8. Conclusion

More than a thousand years later, in the north of an Island far away, where Cicero had never been, there was a place to study his Oratory lessons. If we are not vigilant enough, we may analyse the manuals and the surviving documents, the fruit of those manuals, with the same measures we investigate Cicero's work. However, everything had literally changed. Latin was no longer the native language anywhere in Western Europe by the late Middle Ages, regardless of some people who could start learning it as soon as five or six years old. There was no political regime similar to the Roman Republic, where the power was divided into several spheres and, in each sphere, several hands; the sources of power were slowly combining each other to what would be known as Absolutism a few centuries later. The Roman Laws were no longer, overridden by a mix of Christian and Germanic Laws. The societal structure and the *cursus honorum* Cicero so steadily defended were far different from the complex and mixed reality of each kingdom in Europe throughout the late Middle Ages. In sum, the Roman World of Cicero's *De Oratore* (Fantham, 2012) was no longer.

So, why did medieval people choose to interpret and apply Cicero's theory? How did they do it? And, most of all, what were the results of it? The first step to answer those questions is to acknowledge the fluid historical stream between Cicero, Quintilian, Tacitus, Jerome, Augustine, Alberic of Montecassino, Marbode of Rennes, Geoffrey of Vinsauf, and William of Whalley. It was an extensive line of evolutions and revolutions in the theoretical discussion and practical application of speaking well in public with the objective of receiving support and understanding.

Although the tools and political and legal contexts of Cicero's life and late medieval Durham were highly different, the overarching goal remained the same. Reaching the same objective in various contexts with diverse societies implies distinctive strategies. Nonetheless, William of Whalley did not change the names of the strategies or the rhetorical figures. Still, they changed their values and application—truthfully, it happened throughout the years, from Imperial Rome to the fifteenth century. Here, we usually commit a terrible mistake: we, Western post-modern people, consider that things with similar names must be similar, if not identical. That is entirely wrong and misleading. Cicero's triad *Docere*, *Delectare*, and *Mouere* were meant to give ancient Roman students pillars they could rely on to construct their orations. The same triad can be seen in the

TD, as seen in this article, but each leg represents something partially or distinct, depending on the context and interpretation. If we try to comprehend each pillar in the same format, with the same mechanism, in the late Middle Ages, we will always fail. If we try to see them in late Antiquity, we will fail.

The triad exposes what needs to be done but not how. Cicero himself experienced profound changes in his world. It is hard to believe he would use the same approach to defending Marcellus in his early days. First, because he changed, he evolved, he learned. Second, because the political and juridical scenarios had shifted, he could not act in the same way. The same is true in the Middle Ages. The changes in the composition manuals represent the revolutions within Western and Central Europe well, as brilliantly explained by studies edited by Grévin and Turcan-Verkerk (2015).

The study of the reception and reapplication of ancient Rhetoric in a late medieval medium-sized community in Northeast England offers us a unique opportunity to delve deeper into the fascinating world of Ciceronian Rhetoric - to understand how it evolved, and what was the role of Middle Ages in shaping it, as well as how it evolved. This study presents us with an excellent chance to explore questions related to literacy, consumption of ancient books, educational systems, and the development of societal, political, and legal institutions that were the basis of Modern States. By examining all these aspects, we can gain a better understanding of the intricate interplay between ancient and medieval cultures and how they influenced each other to shape the world we live in today.

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